

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-286-IE-5% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	20	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 286
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	274.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 274.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/28/2023 17:12:25 CST		
Date Processed:	4/4/2023 9:18:07 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.534	268183	14.52	37466
2	7.214	259173	14.03	32576
3	8.137	657545	35.60	70910
4	11.634	662259	35.85	48149

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-287-IE-5% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230403
Vial:	101	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 287
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	274.0nm
Run Time:	17.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 274.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/3/2023 9:31:42 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/4/2023 9:29:21 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.673	18344	1.66	2488
2	7.355	9630	0.87	1178
3	8.271	2444	0.22	359
4	11.660	1074686	97.25	77745